

Belgium | One Health Surveillance | *Salmonella*

Background & Objectives

- Integrate WGS data from human and non-human isolates
- Evaluate the impact of culture-independent diagnostic testing (CIDT) on the surveillance of *Salmonella*
- Harmonize outbreak investigation tools across regions

Outcomes & Impact

- WGS data from human samples is integrated into the BE-prepared architecture, of which the outbreak detection tool is currently being validated
- Surveys among clinical medical laboratories in Belgium confirmed the increased use of CIDT, but also showed their willingness to send samples to the national reference laboratories for surveillance
- A common questionnaire is now available in electronic format for regional health authorities and was already used in a *S. Enteritidis* outbreak

Lessons learned

- To strengthen the One Health surveillance of *Salmonella*, it is essential that data and information is shared among stakeholders
- Sustainable resources are needed for the implementation of routine genomic surveillance
- The use of CIDT and the impact this will have on the surveillance of *Salmonella* has to be monitored on a regular basis

Core messages

In order to achieve a One Health surveillance of *Salmonella*, it is necessary to have:

- A good knowledge of all stakeholders;
- Maintain contact and trust between them;
- Promote and develop tools allowing for data sharing.